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The cover depicts the gentle gaze of AI on our precious earth within the cosmic background

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Editorial

Solidarity and Hope

These are terrible and fearful times. Some 3.55 million people have been infected by COVID-19 and nearly a quarter of a million have perished. Billions of people are on lockdown or in self-isolation, uncertain, lonely and afraid.

Yet this pandemic and the fear, dread, and anxiety that it has caused has led to an increase in solidarity, write Ulrika Modéer and Anna Ryott at United Nations Development Programme (Modeer & Ryott, 2020).

No one doubts that COVID-19 is one of the most serious threats the world has ever faced. And yet, amidst the confusion and anxiety, there are ever stronger signs of hope and solidarity, a sense of, and desire for, togetherness.

It is this spirit of global togetherness that gives us hope. In this time of crisis, we are all neighbours in the world, and success will only be achieved when all people, in all countries, are protected.

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Thankfully, this shared sense of responsibility has seen a world come together in ways that we have not seen for some time, and the examples are everywhere.

The New York Times reports about a special situation in the United Kingdom: “When the government appealed recently for 250,000 people to help the National Health Service, more than 750,000 signed up. They had to stop taking applicants so it could process the flood.”

In Somalia, where health infrastructure and traditional media have suffered under decades of strife, local storytellers are being equipped with the skills and tools to reach remote communities and educate them on best practices against COVID-19 (Modeer & Ryott, 2020).

Without ignoring the terrible and tragic realities we face, it is clear that the world is reaching for a positive message. These words were echoed by UN Secretary-General António Guterres to world leaders, as he emphasized the need for solidarity and global cooperation.

His call has resonated. Long sought-after partnerships with private sector companies are suddenly coming to fruition as everyone steps up to pitch in. UNDP has recently partnered with Variety on global ad campaigns to promote the awareness about COVID-19 pandemic.

The four articles in this issue deal with articles on science, philosophy and religion, which will bring depth and meaning to our lives.

May we be agents of solidarity and hope in these troubled times!
May we learn lessons from this pandemic so that we may truly live like brothers and sisters.

The Editor

Modeer, U., & Ryott, A. (2020, May 5). *COVID-19: A reminder of the power of hope and solidarity*. United Nations Development Programme. <https://www.undp.org/blogs/covid-19-reminder-power-hope-and-solidarity>